

**5th International Conference on STEM Teacher Education:
21st Century Challenges**

**Engaging STEM Education Through Educational Videogames:
Present and Future Possibilities**

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TOPICS: STEM Education in the Digital Era, Interdisciplinarity in STEM Education, Proposal for Workshop

Educational Videogames, Interactive Learning, Universal Design for Learning, Flipped Classroom

1. Innovative Learning Through Educational Videogames: Purpose and Impact

How can educational video games make STEM learning fun, inclusive, and impactful? This workshop will introduce two multilingual games designed for school-aged children, covering cutting-edge science topics like micro- and nanoplastics pollution ([Microplastic Madness: Catching PlastikPunk](#)) and 3D bioprinting ([Tissue Trek: The Scaffold Safari](#)). Participants will explore how these tools promote skill-building in different science fields, critical thinking, problem-solving, and interdisciplinarity while catering to diverse learning needs. Leveraging the global appeal of gaming, players embark on adventures combining multiple-choice challenges and coding instructions to complete missions. Developed within the European Horizon 2020 projects [Imptox](#) and [InterLynk](#), these games are available online for free, ensuring accessibility across different countries. They can be seamlessly integrated into classrooms as innovative educational tools for the digital era.

The workshop will also present our vision for a future digital platform where students themselves will be able to develop educational video games. This proposed platform will enable high school students to create educational content for their peers or younger students, building their skills in programming, mathematics, logical reasoning, and foreign languages. We envision the development of a portal/website where a community of creators can publish their games, and educators and users can access a curated catalog of games on specific topics. The platform will enable users to play, evaluate, and adapt the games to create new, enhanced versions. All games created through the platform will be

made available under a Creative Commons framework, fostering open sharing and offering limitless possibilities for innovation, collaboration and interdisciplinary learning.

2. Workshop Highlights: Added Value and Theoretical Framework

The workshop will be valuable for both participants and presenters. Participants will learn about these new and innovative educational tools, gaining hands-on experience in their use, while presenters will be provided valuable feedback to improve them further for diverse uses in and outside the classroom. Additionally, participants will help shape the future of the envisioned digital platform, contributing to a student-driven approach to educational content creation.

The workshop addresses 21st-century challenges in STEM education through interdisciplinary, digital approaches with a vision towards a future where students themselves become active participants in teaching. The theoretical foundation is based on Universal Design for Learning (UDL), ensuring resources meet diverse learning needs. It aligns with the flipped classroom model, where students create educational tools that support peer learning, and draws on constructionist learning theories, which emphasize learning by creating tangible products.

3. Interactive Workshop Format: Engaging Participants

The workshop will introduce the educational video games, outlining their objectives, content, and impact on STEM education along with the vision for expanding into the described digital platform. Participants will engage directly with both games using their own devices. Following this hands-on experience, a feedback session will be held to gather essential insights on enhancing the games and further developing the envisioned platform concept. The workshop is designed to be highly participatory, with all attendees playing an active role in shaping the vision for the future development of student-created educational content.

Acknowledgement

These educational materials have been developed with support from the European Commission through the Horizon 2020 projects Imptox (965173) and InterLynk (953169).

References

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